

BUILDING AN AERODYNAMIC MODEL OF A VERTICAL LANDING REUSABLE LAUNCHER BASED ON CFD AND WIND TUNNEL EXPERIMENTS IN SALTO AND CFD4SALTO

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ABSTRACT

Since the Falcon 9 first stage successfully landed the first time in 2015, the perception of reusability of launchers has drastically changed. While it was formerly considered a costly, complex and unprofitable solution, it is now seen as indispensable for the cost effective and environmentally friendly space transport.

In this context, the SALTO (reusable Strategic Space Launcher Technologies & Operations) project, funded by the European Union in the frame of the Horizon Europe programme, is supporting the ESA Themis programme in which a demonstrator for a vertically landing launcher first stage is built. A first version for this demonstrator is propelled by one Prometheus engine with about 120 t thrust and performs simple trajectories. This version is called T1H, where the H stands for the “Hop Test” to be performed. A later version, called the Themis 3 or T3, shall have 3 engines and perform more complex flight trajectories. In SALTO the Hop Test of T1H is performed and technologies for the T3 vehicle are matured. In the ESA FLPP project CFD4SALTO, CFD computations for the generation of the aerodynamic databases of the T3 vehicle are performed and the extrapolation of wind tunnel experiments to flight are investigated.

The task of the DLR in SALTO is, among others, the aerodynamic design of the T3 vehicle. This paper summarizes how the aerodynamic model of the T3 vehicle is set up. First the strategy for the aerodynamic modelling is described. Then, the various flight configurations are defined. Consequently, the strategies and mathematical formulations are elaborated which are applied to reduce the large amount of necessary data points. Afterwards, low-fidelity computations (generated in SALTO) and high-fidelity computations (generated in CFD4SALTO) are compared to show to which extent simplified modelling approaches can be used for the sizing and aerodynamic design, but to also highlight their limitations. Lastly, the

paper discusses first wind tunnel experiments performed in the Trisonic Wind Tunnel Cologne (TMK) for the assessment of the aerodynamic performance of the configuration and for the verification of the modelling approaches.

Index Terms— Reusable Launch Vehicle, Retro-Propulsion, Wind Tunnel Tests, CFD, Aerodynamics, SALTO

1 INTRODUCTION

In 2015 the SpaceX Falcon 9 successfully landed for the first time. This marked a change in the perception of reusable launch vehicles. While before that the Space Shuttle program had shaped the common opinion that reusable launch vehicles are not necessarily more cost efficient than expendable ones, suddenly the approach of reusing the first stage with the help of descending and landing it back on the launch pad or on a sea going platform seemed very promising for large potential cost savings.

Several projects were started in Europe to deal with Vertical Take-off Vertical Landing (VTVL) launcher configurations. In Ariane Next [1] and ENTRAIN [2, 3] system studies were performed, in EAGLE [4], FROG [5] and DTV [6] small scale demonstrators for GNC development were designed, wind tunnel experiments and CFD tools were validated for such applications in RETPRO [7], key technologies for retro propulsive descent and landing were investigated in the RETALT project [8, 9], an open source project is aiming to study aerodynamics and aerothermodynamics of vertically landing launcher first stages [10] and finally projects like CALLISTO [11] and Themis [12] focus on large scale demonstrators.

The SALTO (reusable Strategic Space Launcher Technologies & Operations) project can be seen in this context. It is funded by the European Union in the frame of the Horizon Europe programme and supports the ESA Themis programme in which a demonstrator for a vertically landing launcher first stage is built.

In Fig. 1 the various scenarios that are investigated in SALTO are sketched. The main part of SALTO is focused on the T1H configuration. This is a demonstrator with one Prometheus engine with which a hop test will be performed in SALTO. In addition, future launcher configurations are investigated which are representative of full-scale launchers. This study also serves to evaluate how well technologies scale from the demonstrator to full-scale vehicles. To keep the technological steps to be taken between the T1H and the future launcher configurations smaller, an intermediate demonstrator reference configuration with three Prometheus engines, namely the T3, is investigated. This is the reference configuration which could be build and developed further after the T1H vehicle. With this demonstrator a representative flight altitude and trajectory could be realized including all relevant flight phases of a vertically landing first stage, including the re-entry burn, the aerodynamic phase and the landing burn.

The scenarios are studied with different levels of detail in SALTO. T1H is at a high TRL (Technology Readiness Level) as it will be flown in the project lifetime. T3 is studied in detail with dedicated analyses of aerodynamics, aerothermodynamics, flight dynamics, structures and thermal protection systems. The future launcher configurations are studied on a concept level with low TRL.

The German Aerospace Center (DLR) is involved in SALTO with eight Departments from three Institutes of four sites in Germany: Cologne, Göttingen, Braunschweig and Bremen. The Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology in Cologne, Göttingen and Braunschweig is responsible for the aerodynamic and aerothermal design of the T3 with extensive computational fluid dynamics simulations and wind tunnel testing. The Institute for Space Systems in Bremen will support the system design for the hop tests demonstrator with tests and simulations of landing dynamics (see ref. [13]). Technologies for intra-vehicular wireless communication and a hybrid navigation system, including a health monitoring system of the Institute of Space Systems in Bremen will fly on the vehicle. Health monitoring systems for actuators are being designed by the Institute of Flight Systems and will also be flown. Furthermore, the Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology and the Institute for Space Systems are responsible for the assessment of the scalability of the technologies developed for the demonstrators to full scale vehicles.[14]

The ESA FLPP project CFD4SALTO is closely related to the SALTO project. In CFD4SALTO high-fidelity computations are generated for the aerodynamic databases of T3 in SALTO. In addition, the extrapolation of the wind tunnel experiments to flight conditions are investigated numerically. The partners of the CFD4SALTO project are the DLR, with its Supersonic and Hypersonic Technologies Department in Cologne, and CFS Engineering. The DLR is leading the

project and is responsible for the aeroshape, the aerodynamic database and the processing of wind tunnel data from SALTO for the use in CFD4SALTO. CFSE is responsible for the computations to be performed in the project and for their evaluation.

Fig. 1: Sketch of configurations investigated in SALTO

This paper focuses on the generation of the aerodynamic model of the T3 vehicle based on the data generated and gathered in SALTO and CFD4SALTO. First the aerodynamic modelling is described. Then, the various flight configurations are defined. Consequently, the strategies and mathematical formulations are elaborated which are applied to reduce the large amount of necessary data points. Afterwards, low-fidelity computations (generated in SALTO) and high-fidelity computations (generated in CFD4SALTO) are compared to show to which extent

simplified modelling approaches can be used for the sizing and aerodynamic design, but to also highlight their limitations. Lastly, the paper discusses first wind tunnel experiments performed in the Trisonic Wind Tunnel Cologne (TMK) for the assessment of the aerodynamic performance of the configuration and for the verification of the modelling approaches.

2 AERODYNAMIC MODELLING METHODOLOGY

The general approach of generating a holistic aerodynamic model is as follows. The aerodynamic model is based on aerodynamic databases which are generated in design loops with increasing fidelity. A first aerodynamic database is generated with low-fidelity CFD computations based on laminar computations with inviscid walls and low grid resolutions, such that the computational resources required for its generation are low and the aerodynamic data base can be generated in a short time frame. This first dataset possesses relatively high uncertainties, but it is well suited for the first assessment of the performance of the vehicle and its flying qualities. This way, necessary design modifications can be introduced early in the aerodynamic design process. With the knowledge of the general aerodynamic properties, the dataset of high-fidelity computations to be performed are defined. These computations are based on fully turbulent RANS (Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes) simulations including boundary layers. Dedicated investigations are further performed for the grid fins, unsteady effects, as well as aerothermal computations for the generation of an aerothermal database. The CFD computations also help in defining the wind tunnel tests.

As soon as wind tunnel test results are available, the comparison of the wind tunnel test results with CFD results helps to validate both methodologies. Furthermore, differences are used for the estimation of overall uncertainties in the aerodynamic databases.

When the loop is closed the knowledge of the aerodynamic behaviour of the vehicle can be used for design optimizations. The aerodynamic databases are used in flying qualities analyses, flight dynamics and GNC evaluation and design [15], and the pressure and temperature loads are used for the structural and thermal protection system design.

The low-fidelity computations, the aerothermal computations, the grid fin computations and the unsteady computations are performed by DLR with the DLR flow solver TAU. The high-fidelity computations are performed with the NSMB (Navier Stokes Multi Block) solver by CFSE. The aerothermal computations are described in detail in ref. [16], the grid fin computations are presented in ref. [17] the unsteady simulations are described in ref. [18] and the high-fidelity simulations are discussed in ref. [19].

The wind tunnel experiments throughout the project are performed at the Supersonic and Hypersonic Technologies department of the DLR in Cologne. The aerodynamic phase of the vehicle is investigated with force and moment measurements and with high frequency pressure measurements in the Trisonic Wind Tunnel Cologne (TMK). Also the re-entry burn will be tested in the TMK, where the exhaust plume is simulated with pressurized air. The landing burn is tested in the Hot Plume Testing Facility (HPTF) which is the Vertical Free-Jet Facility Cologne (VMK) together with an oxygen/hydrogen-supply facility. In these experiments the exhaust plume is generated with hot combustion products form a combustion chamber inside the wind tunnel model.

3 VEHICLE DEFINITIONS

3.1 Configurations

The T3 trajectory was provided by Ariane Group and reaches altitudes of about 100 km. As sketched in Fig. 1 after the Main Engine Cut-Off (MECO) a flip over manoeuvre is performed. Followed by a re-entry burn which aims at lowering heat loads and dynamic pressure in the following aerodynamic phase. After the aerodynamic phase follows the final deceleration with the landing burn.

The vehicle configurations to cover the complete trajectory are shown in Fig. 2. The definition of the vehicle configurations are similar to the ones already used in Callisto [20, 21], RETALT [22] and RETPRO [23] before. The vehicle configuration is defined by the configuration of the grid fins, landing legs and operational engines:

- 1st letter: state of the grid fins
(U = unfolded, F = folded, N = no aerodynamic control surfaces (plain configuration))
- 2nd letter: state of the landing legs
(U = unfolded, F = folded)
- 3rd letter: state of the engines
(N = no thrust, number of engines running)

3.2 Aeroshape and reference frame

The aeroshape of the T3 vehicle is shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. The body fixed reference frame is shown with the index f. Additionally the AEDB-coordinate-system (Coordinate System - COSY) for the aerodynamic computations is shown (without any index). The origin of the reference point of the AEDB-COSY is in the bottom of the Multi Engine Bay (MEB) structure, on the base plane of the launcher. The x-axis is pointing rearwards, in the direction from the tip to the bottom of the configuration. The z-axis is pointing upwards and the y-axis is completing the right-handed coordinate system. The reference diameter is 3.5 m, the length is

approx. 29 m (from the base to the tip excluding the interstage and fairing).

Trajectory Phase	Gid Fins	Landing Legs	Active Engines	Configuration
Ascent	Folded	Folded	0	FFN
Ascent	Folded	Folded	1	FF1
Ascent	Folded	Folded	3	FF3
Unpropelled descent	Unfolded	Folded	0	UFN
Landing Burn	Unfolded	Folded	1	UF1
Re-entry Burn	Unfolded	Folded	2	UF2

Fig. 2: Configurations of T3

Fig. 3: Reference frame for the aerodynamic coefficients of T3 - ascent configuration

Fig. 4: Reference frame for the aerodynamic coefficients of T3 - descent configuration

3.3 Freestream angles

The attitude of the vehicle is commonly described with the angle of attack α and the sideslip angle β . However, in the case of vertically landing launchers, the complete globe of possible angles of attack and roll angles need to be covered without creating singularities e.g. to cover situations like the flip over manoeuvre. Hence, an alternative definition of the flight velocity vector is adopted as defined in refs. [21, 23], using the total or effective angle of attack α_S and the aerodynamic roll angle ϕ . With these two angles the free stream angles can be defined uniquely as shown in Fig. 6.

The free stream velocity is defined in the AEDB-COSY. The free stream velocity is pointing in the opposite direction of the velocity vector of the vehicle. Hence, the velocity components of the free stream in the x and z-direction ($v_{x,a}$ and $v_{z,a}$) point in the positive direction of the AEDB-COSY, the y-component ($v_{y,a}$) points in the opposite direction. Therefore, the components of the free stream in the AEDB-COSY are connected to the flight velocity vector in the body fixed coordinate system by:

$$v_{x,a} = u \quad (1)$$

$$v_{y,a} = -v \quad (2)$$

$$v_{z,a} = w \quad (3)$$

Fig. 5: Definition of the free stream velocity components ($v_{x,a}$, $v_{y,a}$, $v_{z,a}$ in red)

Fig. 6: Globe of free stream conditions with α_s and ϕ [21]

4 SUPERPOSITION OF GRID FIN DEFLECTIONS

For the aerodynamic database, computing all possible combinations of the fin deflections would result in far too many computations. Hence, a superposition approach is applied to compute the combinations. This superposition approach was already presented in refs. [21, 23] and was then adapted for the needs of SALTO. Fig. 7 shows the definition of the grid fins in SALTO (view on the rear of the vehicle). Their deflection angles $\delta_1 \dots \delta_4$ are defined positive in the mathematically positive sense around the individual fin axis, pointing from the vehicle longitudinal axis towards the tip of the fin. In the following the configurations will be defined with $[\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3, \delta_4]$.

Fig. 7: Numbering of the fins and positive deflection angles

To reduce the number of computations, only fin 1 is deflected. The complete dataset, e.g. an angle of attack range of α_s of 160° to 180° and ϕ from -180° to 180° is computed for the desired deflections, e.g. $\delta_1 = [-20^\circ, 0^\circ, 20^\circ]$. Hence, all angles of attack and roll angles need to be computed for three deflections.

Then the configuration with deflected fin, is subtracted from the configuration with undeflected fin (hence $[0,0,0,0]$) to obtain the impact of the fin deflection (the delta) on the force and moment coefficients C :

$$\Delta C_i(Ma, \phi, \alpha_s, \delta_i) = C(Ma, \phi, \alpha_s, \delta_i) - C(Ma, \phi, \alpha_s, \delta_{1,2,3,4} = 0) \quad (4)$$

where i is the index of the fin and C represents the force coefficients C_{F_x} , C_{F_y} , C_{F_z} and moment coefficient C_{M_x} , C_{M_y} , C_{M_z} .

Another possibility would be to separate the force coefficient only acting on the grid fin from the overall force coefficient. The superposition could then be performed by adding the deflected fin value to the force or moment coefficient of the plain body without fin. However, the deflection of the fin also changes the flow field around the cylindrical main body. This effect would not be covered in this second approach. However, subtracting the overall coefficients also includes changes due to the interaction with the main body.

The fin then needs to be matched onto the position of the other fins and the superposition of the overall force or moment coefficient can then be performed by adding the coefficient with 0° deflections with the deltas of the fins:

$$C = C(Ma, \phi, \alpha_s, \delta_{1,2,3,4} = 0) + \sum_{i=1}^4 \Delta C_i(Ma, \phi, \alpha_s, \delta_i) \quad (5)$$

With this approach it needs to be noted that there are still two assumptions that are considered to be valid:

- It is assumed that the impact of the deflections of the fins can be considered to be independent. So, by deflecting one fin the value of another deflected fin is not changed.
- It is assumed that all fins show the same behaviour. However, in Fig. 7 it can be seen, that the fins 2 and 3 are positioned downstream of protrusions that will somehow influence the flow field reaching them.

Matching the delta of fin 1 to the positions of the other fins can be performed in two ways. Fig. 8 shows the first strategy by rotating the fin to the other fin positions. This strategy was used in CALLISTO and REPTRO in refs. [21, 23]. Fig. 9 shows the second strategy. Instead of rotating the fin, it is mirrored to the other fins' positions. The necessary formulas are also stated in the figures. In the second variant if the fin is mirrored once, onto fin 2 or 4, also the sign of the fin deflection needs to be inverted. To reach fin 3, fin 1 is mirrored twice, once on the xy and once of the xz-plane. Hence the sign of the deflection stays the same. Furthermore, it shall be noted that for both variants, as the roll angle is adjusted by adding the respective angle of the fin with respect to fin 1, the roll angle needs to be normalized to be in the range of the aerodynamic database which is defined to be from -180° to 180° .

The advantage of the second option is, that the asymmetric features are not rotated with the fin. This is especially obvious as the T3 has three engines and in the rotation strategy the engines rotated with the fin. As the overall coefficient of the configuration with 0° deflections is subtracted from the overall coefficient of the deflected configuration, this effect should not result in large errors as the features that do not change with the deflection should be subtracted. However, the second strategy of mirroring the fin instead of rotating omits this problem at least for the engines as they are symmetric with respect to the xy and xz-plane. Other protrusions that are not symmetric in the xy and xz-plane will be mirrored.

Another advantage of the second strategy of mirroring the fin onto the other fin positions is, that the force and moment coefficients in every direction are independent of each other. Hence the C_{M_y} of fin 2, 3 and 4 is only compute with C_{M_y} of fin 1. C_{F_y} for the fins is only computed with C_{F_y} of fin 1 and so forth. For the first strategy this is not the case. E.g. C_{F_y} of fin two is computed with C_{F_z} of fin 1, while fin 3 is indeed computed with C_{F_y} of fin 1. As the data is not coming from the same direction, the values will slightly vary. Hence for symmetric configuration, the deltas of the fins do not completely cancel each other out.

For example consider the configuration providing maximum pitch moment [20,20,-20,-20]. Recall (Fig. 7) that this means

that all fins are deflected downwards to provide maximum pitch moment. For this configuration the side force (C_{F_y}) of the fins should cancel out, such that just the side force of the configuration with 0° deflections remains. For the strategy 1, this would not be the case while for strategy 2 the grid fin deltas completely cancel out.

Furthermore, for the first strategy the fins which are symmetric with respect to the xz-plane use different roll angles, i.e. fin 2 and 3 have $+180^\circ$ and $+90^\circ$ in the roll angle with regard to fin 1, similarly fin 2 has a roll angle shift of $+90^\circ$ with respect to fin 1. While for the second strategy, the fins 2 and 3 have both shifts of 180° with respect to fin 1, and fin 4 has no shift. So symmetric fins are using the same roll angle data points in the database for strategy 2, while for strategy 1 they use different ones. As the datapoint will always be exposed to some degree of uncertainty also e.g. the CM_x value does not cancel out completely even though the values are all taken directly from fin 1 as they don't refer to the same roll angle datapoint in the database.

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 \phi(F2) = \text{norm}(\phi(F1) - 90^\circ) & \phi(F3) = \text{norm}(\phi(F1) + 180^\circ) & \phi(F4) = \text{norm}(\phi(F1) + 90^\circ) \\
 \Delta C_{F_x}(F2) = \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_x}(F3) = \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_x}(F4) = \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) \\
 \Delta C_{F_y}(F2) = -\Delta C_{F_y}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_y}(F3) = -\Delta C_{F_y}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_y}(F4) = \Delta C_{F_y}(F1) \\
 \Delta C_{F_z}(F2) = \Delta C_{F_z}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_z}(F3) = -\Delta C_{F_z}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_z}(F4) = -\Delta C_{F_z}(F1) \\
 \Delta C_{M_x}(F2) = \Delta C_{M_x}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_x}(F3) = \Delta C_{M_x}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_x}(F4) = \Delta C_{M_x}(F1) \\
 \Delta C_{M_y}(F2) = -\Delta C_{M_y}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_y}(F3) = -\Delta C_{M_y}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_y}(F4) = \Delta C_{M_y}(F1) \\
 \Delta C_{M_z}(F2) = \Delta C_{M_z}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_z}(F3) = -\Delta C_{M_z}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_z}(F4) = -\Delta C_{M_z}(F1)
 \end{array}$$

Fig. 8: Strategies of superposition - rotation

$$\begin{array}{lll}
\phi(F2) = -\text{norm}(\phi(F1) - 180^\circ) & \phi(F3) = \text{norm}(\phi(F1) - 180^\circ) & \phi(F4) = -\phi(F1) \\
\Delta C_{F_x}(F2) = \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_x}(F3) = \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_x}(F4) = \Delta C_{F_x}(F1) \\
\Delta C_{F_y}(F2) = \Delta C_{F_y}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_y}(F3) = -\Delta C_{F_y}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_y}(F4) = -\Delta C_{F_y}(F1) \\
\Delta C_{F_z}(F2) = -\Delta C_{F_z}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_z}(F3) = -\Delta C_{F_z}(F1) & \Delta C_{F_z}(F4) = \Delta C_{F_z}(F1) \\
\Delta C_{M_x}(F2) = -\Delta C_{M_x}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_x}(F3) = \Delta C_{M_x}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_x}(F4) = -\Delta C_{M_x}(F1) \\
\Delta C_{M_y}(F2) = -\Delta C_{M_y}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_y}(F3) = -\Delta C_{M_y}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_y}(F4) = \Delta C_{M_y}(F1) \\
\Delta C_{M_z}(F2) = \Delta C_{M_z}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_z}(F3) = -\Delta C_{M_z}(F1) & \Delta C_{M_z}(F4) = -\Delta C_{M_z}(F1) \\
\delta_2 = -\delta_1 & & \delta_4 = -\delta_1
\end{array}$$

Fig. 9: Strategies of superposition - mirroring

5 RESULTS

5.1 Comparison of low-fidelity and high-fidelity CFD

In this section the low-fidelity data is compared to the high-fidelity CFD computations generated in SALTO and CFD4SALTO. The low-fidelity data was based on laminar computations assuming inviscid walls. The high-fidelity data was computed assuming fully turbulent flow including boundary layers.

In the first aerodynamic database, the uncertainties were set to a high, very conservative value of 25%, as they were based on experience from previous projects, but no detailed analysis was performed yet. Later in the project this value was reduced based on the comparison of low-fidelity and high-fidelity data. While it cannot be reasoned that this comparison can cover all possible uncertainties, it still gives a good estimation for the order of magnitude, as two different codes, modelling approaches and grid refinements were used. Hence, if the two approaches agree well, this gives some level of confidence that the data is reasonable.

Fig. 10 shows one exemplary comparison of the low-fidelity and high-fidelity databases (all fins deflected 0°). This example is notable as it was observed that for an angle of attack (α_s) of 175° the axial force coefficient changes

completely. This effect was later attributed to flow field phenomena which are described in detail in ref. [19]. Hence, the comparison of the datasets also helps identifying critical points, which need to be considered with extra care. Due to the change in the flow field these points are also difficult to handle with uncertainties as they don't show as slight offsets from the rest of the data but can show sudden jumps. This is can be seen in Fig. 11 where the complete angle of attack and roll angle range is plotted for the same Mach number. It can be observed how the behaviour of the axial force coefficient abruptly changes at $\alpha_s = 175^\circ$.

Fig. 10 also shows the data of the low-fidelity computations with the initially assumed uncertainties. It can be seen that, except for the case with changing flow field, the uncertainties for this case can be reduced.

Fig. 10: Example of comparison of low-fidelity data (dots) with high-fidelity data (triangles) for UF2 configuration and $\phi = 0^\circ$ for $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ]$

Fig. 11: 3D plot of high-fidelity data for UF2 configuration with sudden jump in the coefficient at $\alpha_s = 175^\circ$

Fig. 13 shows an analysis that was performed for the UFN configuration in the aerodynamic phase. Here the grid fin deltas were superimposed onto the 0° configuration as described in section 4 (with the mirroring strategy), and all fins were deflected to generate maximum roll moment. It can be seen that the roll moment is relatively independent of the angle of attack. In Fig. 12 the descent trajectory of the T3 vehicle is shown with the points of the computation matrix for the UFN configuration during the aerodynamic phase. The images in Fig. 13 are ordered by increasing altitude. One can see that up to the Mach number of 3.5 the comparison shows that the low-fidelity computations give a very good first approximation of the actual data. Even in the transonic regime, where larger deviations would be expected with such simplified approaches, the coefficients are in good agreement. However, at higher altitudes (Mach 2.5) the differences start to increase. This might be due to thickening of the boundary layers in the grid fins, which leads to blockage, which is not covered in the low-fidelity computations which assume inviscid walls. At high altitudes, the dynamic pressure is very low, as can be seen in Fig. 13, where the dynamic pressure is shown for every plotted Mach number. Hence the efficiency of the grid fins is very low, even if the force coefficients would be large. Therefore, in later iterations of the aerodynamic database the computations were focused on lower altitudes. In general, the supersonic Mach number regime showed better agreement than the subsonic regime.

Fig. 12: Descent trajectory of T3 including data points of the UFN configuration in the aerodynamic phase (burn phases in blue)

Fig. 13: Comparison of roll moment of low-fidelity data (dots) with high-fidelity data (triangles) for UFN configuration with all fins deflected for maximum roll moment

5.2 Validation of superimposed coefficients with wind tunnel data

The approach of superposition of the deflection deltas with the undeflected case were validated in the TMK wind tunnel test series. For that aim, runs were performed with the single grid fin 1 deflected and were then superimposed. These were then compared to runs where all four fins were deflected.

First, the pitch configuration shall be analysed, were all fins are deflected symmetrically with respect to the xz -plane to generate the maximum pitch moment. In Fig. 14 the comparison is shown for the rotation strategy for Mach 0.9 and 3.0, were the solid lines represent the runs with all fins deflected and the dashed lines show the superposition

approach. It can be seen that C_{M_x} of the superimposed configurations does not resemble the configuration with 0° deflection exactly (yellow line). However, the error is only in the order of 0.02 of the C_{M_x} value. Also the pitch moment around the centre of gravity ($C_{M_{yCoG}}$) is rebuilt very well for both Mach numbers. In Fig. 15 the comparison is shown for the second strategy of mirroring the fins. Here it can be seen that the superimposed solutions follow the C_{M_x} of the run with all fins undeflected. Hence, the fin deltas cancel out as expected. The pitch moment coefficient is equally well rebuilt as for the first strategy.

In figure Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 the results are shown for both strategies for the roll moments for the roll configuration where all fins are deflected in the same direction to generate maximum roll moment. It can be seen that both strategies also rebuild this configuration well with only small errors. While the rotation strategy seems to be slightly better in this case. Hence, it can be concluded that the superposition of the deflection of only one fin onto the complete launcher seems to be valid, and the assumptions taken in section 4 are valid, which are that the deflections of the fins can be considered to be independent of each other and that the effect of the protrusions on the performance of the grid fins is not large enough to compromise this approach.

Interpretation of the figures Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 shows that the vehicle is generally stable in the pitch configuration and only small roll moments are generated. Around α_S of 180° a small unstable region can be observed. Therefore, it is important to resolve the databases enough at small angles of attack to cover these effects. Fig. 17 shows that in the roll configuration the roll moment is relatively independent of the angle of attack.

It shall be noted that for the wind tunnel experiments the wall thickness of the grid fins needed to be slightly increased for manufacturing purposes. Furthermore, the Reynolds numbers could not be reproduced exactly. Therefore, extrapolation from wind tunnel experiments to full flight will be performed by comparison of the results of the wind tunnel experiments with dedicated CFD computations of the experiments. Furthermore, dedicated experiments with single grid fins will be performed in the TMK in the remainder of the project.

A detailed analysis of the data of all tested Mach numbers and configurations is still to be performed in the future.

6 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper the methodology of generating the aerodynamic model of T3 in SALTO was laid out. It is based on a combination of low-fidelity and high-fidelity CFD computations and wind tunnel experiments.

First the flight configurations to be considered were defined, followed by the definition of the reference frames and free

stream angles. This definition was based on principles developed in the CALLISTO [20, 21] and in RETPRO [23]. Furthermore, a mathematical model for the superposition of the grid fin deflections on the configuration with undeflected fins was developed based on previous work in CALLISTO [21] and in RETPRO [23]. It is based on the idea of only deflecting one fin and superimposing it on the other grid fin positions. As the T3 configuration is not quarter-symmetric due to its three engines, the methodology was adapted in a manner to leverage the separate symmetry in the xy and xz-planes.

In the results the low-fidelity computations were compared to the high-fidelity computations. They generally show a good agreement over the whole Mach number range from subsonic up to supersonic Mach numbers. However, for the high altitudes the deviations increase due to boundary layer effects in the grid fins which are neglected in the low-fidelity computations.

It was shown that the comparison of high-fidelity and low-fidelity data can be useful for the identification of computation points where the flow field changes and which, therefore, need special consideration as the aerodynamic behaviour can change abruptly.

The superposition method was validated with wind tunnel test data from force and moment measurements in the Trisonic Wind Tunnel Cologne (TMK). The results show that the assumptions taken in the approach, that the deflection of single fins can be considered to be independent of each other, and that the protrusions do not greatly change the flow field around the grid fins, seem to be valid.

In the remainder of SALTO and CFD4SALTO a second loop of the aerodynamic database generation is performed. The aeroshape was adapted to inputs from various disciplines in the project and the influence of these design parameters are studied with high-fidelity CFD computations. Furthermore, the complete dataset will be computed with low-fidelity computations.

Additionally, the force and moments measurements and pressure measurements performed in the TMK will be evaluated further and will be compared to steady and unsteady CFD simulations and uncertainties shall be derived for the datasets.

The comparison of the cold gas experiments in TMK and of the hot gas experiments in the HPTF with CFD computations will further contribute to the validation of the CFD for the propulsive phases and uncertainties will be derived from this data, for the aerodynamic coefficients as well as for the aerothermal loads.

Fig. 14: Coefficients with rotation - pitch configuration

Fig. 15: Coefficients with mirroring - pitch configuration

Fig. 16: Coefficients with rotation - roll configuration

Fig. 17: Coefficients with mirroring - roll configuration

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8 REFERENCES

- [1] Patureau de Mirand, A., Bahu, J.-M., and Louaas, E., "Ariane Next, a vision for a reusable cost efficient European rocket," *8th European Conference for Aeronautics and Space Sciences*, Madrid, Spain, 2019 <https://www.eucass.eu/doi/EUCASS2019-0949.pdf>.
- [2] Stappert, S., Wilken, J., Bussler, L., Sippel, M., Karl, S., Klevanski, J., Hantz, C., Briese, L. E., and Schnepfer, K., "European Next Reusable Ariane (ENTRAIN): A Multidisciplinary Study on a VTVL and a VTHL Booster Stage," *70th International Astronautical Congress*, Washington D.C., USA, 2019, <https://elib.dlr.de/132865/>.
- [3] Wilken, J. and Stappert, S., "Comparative analysis of European vertical landing reusable first stage concepts," *CEAS Space Journal*, Vol. 17, No. 1, 2025, pp. 113-130, 10.1007/s12567-024-00549-9.
- [4] Dumke, M. and Theil, S., "Auto-Coded Flight Software for the GNC VTVL Demonstrator EAGLE," *8th European Conference for Aeronautics and Space Sciences*, Madrid, Spain, 2019, <https://www.eucass.eu/doi/EUCASS2019-0772.pdf>.
- [5] Rmili, B., Monchoux, D., Bosineau, O., Hassin, J., Querry, S., Besson, S., Poirey, G., Boré, R., Hamada, I., Amrouchi, H., Franc, J., Barreau, M., Mercadié, N., Labois, T., and Grinco, D., "FROG, a Rocket for GNC demonstrations: Firsts flights attempts of the FROG turbojet version and preparation of the future monopropellant rocket engine," *8th European Conference for Aeronautics and Space Sciences*, Madrid, Spain, 2019, <https://www.eucass.eu/doi/EUCASS2019-0197.pdf>.
- [6] Neculaescu, A.-M., Marin, A., Toader, A., Persinaru, A.-G., Cismilianu, A.-M., Tudose, M., Munteanu, C.-E., Popescu, I., Strauch, H., and Dussy, S., "System Identification and Testing for a VTVL vehicle", *8th European Conference for Aeronautics and Space Sciences*, 2019, <https://www.eucass.eu/doi/EUCASS2019-0925.pdf>.
- [7] Kirchheck, D., Marwege, A., Klevanski, J., Riehmer, J., Gülhan, A., Karl, S., and Gloth, O., "Validation of Wind Tunnel Test and CFD Technologies for Retro-Propulsion (RETPRO): Overview of a Project within the Future Launcher Preparatory Programme (FLPP)," *International Conference on Flight Vehicles, Aerothermodynamics and Re-entry Missions & Engineering*, 2019, https://elib.dlr.de/137501/1/FAR2019_Kirchheck.pdf.
- [8] Marwege, A., Gülhan, A., Klevanski, J., Hantz, C., Karl, S., Laureti, M., De Zaiacomo, G., Vos, J., Jevons, M., Thies, C., Krammer, A., Lichtenberger, M., Carvalho, J., and Paixão, S., "RETALT: review of technologies and overview of design changes," *CEAS Space Journal*, Vol.

- 14, No. 3, 2022, pp. 433-445, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12567-022-00458-9>.
- [9] Marwege, A., Klevanski, J., Hantz, C., Kirchheck, D., Guelhan, A., Karl, S., Laureti, M., Zaiacomio, G. D., Vos, J., Thies, C., Jevons, M., Krammer, A., Lichtenberger, M., Carvalho, J., and Paixão, S., "Key Technologies for Retro Propulsive Vertical Descent and Landing – RETALT – An Overview," *2nd International Conference on Flight Vehicles, Aerothermodynamics and Re-entry Missions and Engineering*, Heibronn, Germany, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6783915>.
- [10] Bykerk, T., "A standard model for the investigation of aerodynamic and aerothermal loads on a re-usable launch vehicle," *10th EUCASS - 9th CEAS*, Lausanne, Switzerland, 2023 pp. 1-12. [Online]. Available: <https://elib.dlr.de/194475/>.
- [11] Dumont, E., Woicke, S., Sagliano, M., Krieger, A., Krummen, S., Callsen, S., Stief, M., Bergmann, K., Koch, A., Markgraf, M., Windelberg, J., Eichel, S., Klevanski, J., Ecker, T., Ertl, M., Reimann, B., Mierheim, O., Glaser, T., and Heinrich, L., "CALLISTO Reusable rocket stage demonstrator: consolidating the design," *2024 IEEE Aerospace Conference*, 2024, pp. 1-19, 10.1109/AERO58975.2024.10521353.
- [12] Vila, J. and Hassin, J., "Technology acceleration process for the Themis low cost and reusable prototype," *8th European Conference for Aeronautics and Space Sciences*, Madrid, Spain, 2019, <https://www.eucass.eu/doi/EUCASS2019-0097.pdf>.
- [13] Krämer, C. and Witte, L., "Experimental Investigations of Fluid-to-Vehicle Interactions during a Reusable Launcher's Touchdown Impact," *CEAS Space Journal, PREPRINT (Version 1)*, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4977412/v1>.
- [14] "DLR Website, SALTO – Technologies for Europe's reusable rockets." <https://www.dlr.de/en/research-and-transfer/featured-topics/reusable-space-transportation/salto-technologies-for-europes-first-reusable-rocket> (accessed 14.04.2025).
- [15] Gutiérrez Briceño, J., Medici, G., Princi, A., and De Zaiacomio, G., "Flight Dynamics Evaluation for the T3 Suborbital Flight Test," *3rd International Conference on Flight vehicles, Aerothermodynamics and Re-entry (FAR)*, Arcachon, France, 2025.
- [16] Laureti, M. and Karl, S., "Aerothermal Analysis of Themis T3: Influence of Nozzle Cluster Geometry on the Base Heating and Heat Loads on the Grid Fins," *3rd International Conference on Flight vehicles, Aerothermodynamics and Re-entry (FAR)*, Arcachon, France, 2025.
- [17] Neumann, J., "Parametric grid fin design study for the T3 vehicle within SALTO," *DGLR STAB Symposium*, Regensburg, Deutschland, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://elib.dlr.de/210892/>.
- [18] Horchler, T. and Laureti, M., "Analysis of Unsteady Pressure Loads on the Themis T3 Vehicle in Unpropelled Backward Flight," *3rd International Conference on Flight vehicles, Aerothermodynamics and Re-entry (FAR)*, Arcachon, France, 2025.
- [19] Vos, J., Gehri, A., and Benedetti, G., "Aerodynamic Data Base Generation for a Re-Usable Launcher Configuration," *3rd International Conference on Flight vehicles, Aerothermodynamics and Re-entry (FAR)*, Arcachon, France, 2025.
- [20] Klevanski, J., Ecker, T., Riehmer, J., Reimann, B., Dumont, E., and Chavagnace, C., "Aerodynamic Studies in Preparation for CALLISTO - Reusable VTVL Launcher First Stage Demonstrator," *69th International Astronautical Congress (IAC)*, Bremen, Germany, 2018, <https://elib.dlr.de/122062/>.
- [21] Klevanski, J., Reimann, B., Krummen, S., Ertl, M., Ecker, T., Riehmer, J., and Dumont, E., "Progress in Aerodynamic Studies for CALLISTO - Reusable VTVL Launcher First Stage Demonstrator," *9TH EUROPEAN CONFERENCE FOR AEROSPACE SCIENCES (EUCASS)*, Lille, Frankreich, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://elib.dlr.de/187069/>.
- [22] Marwege, A., Gülhan, A., Klevanski, J., Riehmer, J., Karl, S., Kirchheck, D., Bonetti, D., Vos, J., Jevons, M., Krammer, A., and Carvalho, J., "Retro Propulsion Assisted Landing Technologies (RETALT): Current Status and Outlook of the EU funded project on Reusable Launch Vehicles," Washington D.C., USA, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5770046>.
- [23] Klevanski, J., Kirchheck, D., and Gülhan, A., "Flight Dynamics Simulation and Aerodynamic Database of a Retro-Propulsion Assisted Reusable Launcher Within the RETPRO Project," *International Astronautical Congress (IAC)*, 2024 pp. 987-1001, <https://doi.org/10.52202/078373-0103>.